

A study on customer preference towards two wheelers in Coimbatore city

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Abstract

Within the past decade two wheeler usage indicates a rapid growth in Indian market. Among the two wheeler population, Indian two wheeler brands representing a huge portion. In this research study researcher put effort to find out what are the factors effect on decisions of consumers on two wheelers. Main purpose of this study was to identify why people prefer two wheeler brands becoming more popular and which factors effect on the purchasing decision and open up the gateway to study on this area among this study. Researcher's previous working experience at Automotive Industry was lead to conduct the study. Data were collected from 200 respondents using questionnaire. The findings also revealed several implications for marketers to better segmentation and targeting in the automobile industry especially on two wheeler sales. Further contribution of the demographic factors such as age, gender, distance travelled how far impacted on the purchasing decisions of the two wheelers and those are helpful to marketing managers to develop their strategies.

Keywords: purchasing intension, two wheelers, Coimbatore city

Introduction

The Indian auto industry is one of the largest in the world. The industry accounts for 7.1 per cent of the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The Two Wheelers segment with 80 per cent market share is the leader of the Indian Automobile market owing to a growing middle class and a young population. Moreover, the growing interest of the companies in exploring the rural markets further aided the growth of the sector. The overall Passenger Vehicle (PV) segment has 14 per cent market share. India is also a prominent auto exporter and has strong export growth expectations for the near future. Overall automobile exports grew 15.81 per cent year-on-year between April-February 2017-18. In addition, several initiatives by the Government of India and the major automobile players in the Indian market are expected to make India a leader in the 2W and Four Wheeler (4W) market in the world by 2020. Production of passenger vehicles, commercial vehicles, three wheelers and two wheelers grew at 14.41 per cent year-on-year between April-February 2017-18 to 26,402,671 vehicles. The auto industry is set to witness major changes in the form of electric vehicles (EVs), shared mobility, Bharat Stage-VI emission and safety norms. Electric cars in India are expected to get new green number plates and may also get free parking for three years along with toll waivers. India's electric vehicle (EV) sales increased to 25,000 units during FY 2016-17 and are poised to rise further on the back of cheaper energy storage costs and the Government of India's vision to see six million electric and hybrid vehicles in India by 2020.

Statement of the problem

The necessity of usage of two wheelers is becoming mandatory for today's fast work. The purchase decision is based on their needs and necessities. The earning capacity of

and individual plays a vital role in decision making. Therefore the study focuses on the problems in the usage of two wheelers and the decision among consumers is based on needs and awareness of brands available in Coimbatore city.

Objectives of the study

1. To analyze the preference of the customers with respect to two wheelers.
2. Suggestions to improve market.

Methodology

The researcher used descriptive type of research. This research design deals with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group of customers. Descriptive research includes surveys and fact finding inquires of different kind. In this study the researcher attempted to analyze the customer preferences towards purchasing of two wheelers in the Coimbatore city. So, the descriptive is selected for this study. The researcher used primary and secondary data to collect the details from the respondents. The sample size of this study consists of 200 respondents. Convenient sampling method was used in identifying samples for the study. For analyzing the data, the statistical tools used for the study Simple Percentage Method and Chi-Square Test is used.

Review of literature

Joseph Sarkis, (2007) Green supply chain management: pressures, practices and performance within the Chinese automobile industry this study examines the Chinese automobile supply chain managers to consider and initiate implementation of green supply chain management (GSCM) practices to improve both their economic and environmental performance.

Anna. S. Mattila (2011) the Impact of Other Customers on

Customer Experiences this research examines how other-customer-elicited responses jointly affect the overall customer experience.

Analysis and interpretation

Table 1: Age of the respondents

Age	Count	%
18-21	65	65
22-24	37	37
25-27	40	40
28-30	58	58
Total	200	200

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that maximum 65% of the respondents belong to the age between 18 and 21 years, while 37% of the respondents belong to the age between 22 and 24 years, 40% of the respondents are in the group of 25 to 27 years and the remaining 58% of the respondents are in the age between 28 and 30 years.

Table 2: Gender of the respondents

Gender	Count	%
Male	112	112
Female	88	88
Total	200	200

Source: Primary Data

It is clear that majorities (112%) of the respondents are male and 88% of the respondents are female.

Table 3: Type of two wheeler owned by the respondents

Type of Bike	Count	%
Gear Bike	70	70
Gearless two-wheeler	65	65
Gearless two-wheeler for women	65	65
Total	200	200

Source: Primary Data

It is evident that maximum 70% of the respondents own Gear bikes, whereas, 65% of the respondents own Gearless two wheelers and the remaining 65% of the respondents own Gearless two-wheelers for women.

Table 4: Average distance covered by the respondents

Average Distance	Count	%
5-10	63	63
11-20	54	54
21-30	68	68
31-50	10	10
51-60	5	5
Total	200	200.00

Source: Primary Data

It is understood that 63% of the respondents cover 5 to 10 Kms.in a week, while 54% of the respondents cover from 11 to 20 kms. While 68% of the respondent's covers 21 to 30 kms. a week, whereas, 10% of the respondents covers the

distances of 31-50 kms in a week and the remaining 5% of the respondents covers 51 to 60 kms a week.

Table 5: Purpose of using two wheeler

Purpose of utility	Count	%
Colleges	58	58
Local Trips(Shopping)	54	54
Office	78	78
Recreation	5	5
Others	5	5
Total	100	200

Source: Primary Data

It is understood that maximum 78% of the respondents used their two wheelers for office and 58%for going to colleges whereas 54% for their local trips, while 5% of the respondents used for recreation and the remaining 5% of the respondents used for other purposes.

CHI-Square Test

H₀: There is no significant relationship between purpose of usage of two wheelers and opinion about buying four wheelers
H₁: There is significant relationship between purpose of usage of two wheelers and opinion about buying four wheelers

Table 6: Relationship between purpose of usage of two wheelers and opinion about buying four wheelers

Purpose of usage	What you prefer- two wheeler or four wheeler			Total
	Yes	No	May be	
Colleges	11	14	16	41
Local Trips (Shopping)	5	10	23	38
Office	29	32	29	90
Recreation	5	8	8	21
Others	5	2	3	10
Total	55	66	79	200

Source: Computed from primary data

The result of the chi-square test reveals that the calculated chi-square value is more than the table chi-square value at 5% level of significance and therefore, the relationship between purpose of usage of two wheelers and opinion about buying four wheelers is significant. Thus the hypothesis is that the relationship between the two factors holds good. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Summary of results

Findings

- Maximum 65% of the respondents belong to the age between 18 and 21 years.
- It is clear that majorities (112%) of the respondents are male.
- Maximum 68% of the respondents covers 21 to 30 Kms. a week.
- Maximum 78% of the respondents used their two wheelers for office
- Chi-Square results shows that the calculated chi-square value is more than the table chi-square value at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Suggestions

1. Most of the respondents are willing to purchase two wheelers rather than four wheelers.
2. Majority of the users were found to be men, hence the economical aspects of using the two wheelers reveals such results.

Conclusion

Electric bikes (bikes with electric conversion kits) are part of a wide range of Light Electric Vehicles (LEVs) that provide convenient local transportation. Generally designed for one person and small cargo capacity, electric bike range, speed, and cost are moderate. For most of us, the majority of our trips are less than 20 miles - within the range of most e-bikes considering the latest advances in affordable lithium batteries. Clean, quiet, and efficient LEVs offer the advantages of an extra car without the burdens. If the suggestions provided in the study taken into consideration the challenges shall be changed into prospects to achieve greater heights in the E-Bike markets.

References

1. Mendis MG. Factors affecting purchasing decisions for Indian two wheelers in Sri Lankan market, Kelaniya journal of management. 2015; 4(2).
2. Dr. A Valarmathi. The factors influencing the students behaviour of two wheelers in Tirupur district, International journal of emerging research in management & technology, 2015; 4(12).